

STATUS OF AGRICULTURE IN NORTH EASTERN HILL (NEH) REGION OF INDIA

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The North Eastern Hill (NEH) Region is bounded to the north by Nepal, China and Bhutan, to the east by Myanmar and to the southwest by Bangladesh. It is connected to India to the west by a narrow corridor. Apart from the fertile central plains of Assam bordering the Brahmaputra River and the Barak River, the region is hilly or mountainous, including parts of the Himalayas, the Garo Hills, Khasi and Jaintia Hills, Mikir Hills and North Cachar Hills to the south of the Brahmaputra, the Mishmi Hills in the far east, and the Patkai Range, Naga Hills, Manipur Hills, Lakher Hills and Lushai Hills along the border with Myanmar to the east and southeast. The NEH Region of India comprises seven states viz. Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Tripura and Sikkim, habitats 124 tribal communities. Each tribe has distinct agricultural practices in one way or the other even within a district. The overall population of tribal is around 59.66% of total seven state populations. In which, the highest tribal population is found in Mizoram (94.75%) followed by Nagaland (87.70%), Meghalaya (85.53%), Arunachal Pradesh (63.65%), Manipur (34.41%), Tripura (30.95%) and lowest in Sikkim (20.60%). NEH region occupies about 1.2% human population, 1.5% livestock population and 5.6% geographical area of India with net sown area of 1.76 m ha. Predominantly a rural population (70%), the human density in all the states but Tripura is substantially less than the national average. Almost three quarters (73.87%) of the geographical area of the region is covered with forest as against the national average of 21.55%. However, the states like Manipur, Mizoram and Nagaland have more than 50% area under open forest category and are highly prone to land degradation. Meghalaya also have the similar situation. The region, by and large, is characterized by fragility, marginality, inaccessibility, cultural heterogeneity, diverse ethnicity and rich biodiversity. The region receives an average annual rainfall of about 2000 mm accounting for around 10% (42.5 m ha m) of the country's total precipitation of 420.0 m ha m. Around 56% of the area is under low altitude, 33% mid altitude and the rest under high altitude.

Table: Status of NEH region in India

States	Geographical area(m ha)	Total population (million)	Tribal population (%)	Population density (no/sq km)	Net sown area (m ha)	Total forest area (m ha)	Cropping intensity (%)	Land holding (ha)
Arunachal Pradesh	8.37	1.38	63.65	17	0.225	6.70	137	3.35
Sikkim	0.71	0.61	20.60	86	0.077	0.33	210	1.27
Meghalaya	2.24	2.97	85.53	132	0.286	1.71	123	1.25
Mizoram	2.11	1.10	94.75	52	0.145	1.82	129	1.14
Tripura	1.05	3.67	30.95	350	0.255	0.77	191	0.49
Manipur	2.23	2.86	34.41	128	0.383	1.73	100	1.29
Nagaland	1.66	1.98	87.70	119	0.384	1.25	138	4.87
NEH region	18.37	14.57	59.66	126	1.76	14.31	147	1.95
All India	328.73	1210.20	8.08	325	140.13	70.83	143	1.08

Source: Census (2011). Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt. of India

Jhum, a shifting agriculture technique pertaining to North-Eastern Region of India (NERI) is traditionally being practiced by local tribes from ancient ages. This practice accounts almost 86% of total shifting cultivation area of India. Demographic density, expansion of trade networks, economic and social change are now pushing "Jhum" into increasingly marginal. Most of the local people are gradually moving towards wet or settled cultivation as shifting cultivations hardly have any inclination to produce a surplus. Instead of this transition from shifting to settled cultivation, overall agricultural yield is insufficient to fulfill local need. Among predisposing factors at the background of low agricultural (both shifting and settled cultivations) productivity in NEH, use of local artisans made primitive tools/equipment which are ineffective/not well suited with users physical capacity and incapable of providing better performance for higher efficiency and inadequate irrigation facility are few worthy to mention. Shifting cultivation, locally known as jhum, is the mainstay of economy in most north-eastern hill states except Sikkim. Jhum cultivation is predominant in the region, partly due to social ethos of the various ethnic groups, and partly to topography and prevailing land tenure system. There are various estimates for area under shifting cultivation. Shifting cultivation was considered sustainable so long the jhum cycle was 10-15 years. However, of late, it has been reduced drastically in most of the states to 1-3 years. On average, about

3.85 lakh families are engaged in slash and burn agriculture. Shifting cultivation is considered '**Organic by Default**' mainly because consumption of inorganic fertilizers and other agro-chemicals is very low in the region and hence provides ample opportunity to develop "**Organic Agri-food**" systems hubs. Arunachal Pradesh, followed by Nagaland and Mizoram has the lowest consumption of inorganic fertilizers compared to other states.

The soils are rich in organic matter; acidic to strongly acidic in reaction. The soil depth varies from shallow in inceptisols and antisols to very deep in the alluvial soils. The region being a repository of rich biodiversity is recognized as a '**Climate Marker**'. Different cultural backgrounds of the inhabitants coupled with variable food habits and climatic situations resulted in

cultivation of diverse and mixed crops of cereals, pulses, oilseeds, vegetables, fruits, spices and flowers. Agroforestry, animal husbandry and fisheries are the integral parts of their cropping/farming systems. Around 56% of the area is under low altitude, 33% mid altitude and the rest under high altitude. Agricultural production system is, by and large, Complex, Diverse and Risk prone (CDR). The system is characterized by large variation in cropping intensity (range 100-210% with an average of 147%), mono-cropping and subsistence farming.

Tribes and languages of NEH region of India

The north-eastern part of India is one of the most culturally diverse regions of the world. Inhabited by more than 200 tribes, Northeast India gives the shelter to a variety of tribes living in absolute peace. North-eastern part of India with approximately 220 languages spoken is a bonafide melting point of tremendous socio-cultural interaction. The main languages spoken are Manipuri (Manipur); Khasi, Jaintia, Garo, English (Meghalaya); English, Hindi, Aptani, Monpa (Arunachal Pradesh); Bengali, Kokborok (Tripura); English, Nagamese (Nagaland), Mizo (Mizoram), English, -Nepali, Bhotia, Lepcha (Sikkim).

Topography/geography information of NEH region

The Northeast Indian region can be physio-graphically categorized into the Eastern Himalaya, Northeast India has a predominantly humid sub-tropical climate with hot, humid summers, severe monsoons, and mild winters. The region is covered by the mighty Brahmaputra Barak river systems and their tributaries. Geographically, apart from the Brahmaputra, Barak and Imphal valleys and some flatlands in between the hills of Meghalaya and Tripura, the remaining two-thirds of the area is hilly terrain interspersed with valleys and plains; the altitude varies from almost sea-level to over 7,000 meters (23,000 ft)

above MSL (50m-7000m). The region's high rainfall, averaging around 10,000 millimeters (390 in) and above creates problems of the ecosystem, high seismic activity, and floods. The Brahmaputra plain, like a floating island, varies in altitude from 38 m ASL at Dhubri to 157 m ASL at Pasighat, the place where Brahmaputra debouches from the mountains, after flowing for about 200 km in India, from the Tibetan border to the Assam plain. Most places in the Brahmaputra alluvial plain are less than 100 m above sea level. The other plain areas, besides Brahmaputra plain, are the plains of Cachar and Western Tripura. The heights in these areas range from 16 m ASL at Agartala, the capital of Tripura state, to 97 m ASL at Silchar, on the river Barak. The heights in the hilly terrain range in elevation from 1,200 to 1,500 m ASL for the plateau and hilly states of Meghalaya, Nagaland, Manipur and Mizoram to the towering heights of the Himalayan range, sometimes reaching 7,000 m ASL.

Agro climatic zones of NEH region of India

These broad regions show a wide diversity of climate due to altitudinal, physiographical and edaphic variations contributing to the diversity in the agricultural activities of the people. These geographic regions are further delineated into six distinct agro climatic zones as under: 1) Alpine zone 2) Temperate and sub-alpine zone 3) Sub-tropical hill zone 4) Sub-tropical plain zone 5) Mild-tropical hill zone 6) Mild-tropical plain zone. The important areas and horticultural crops grown under the different agroclimatic zones of NEH region is given in Table.

Table: Agro climatic zones of NEH region of India

S. No.	Agro climatic zones	Physical features	Important areas
1.	Alpine Zone (>3500 m)	Area: 47068 km ² Rainfall: 750 mm Temperature: Maximum: 17 ⁰ C Minimum: 2 ⁰ C	Arunachal Pradesh: Gorichen, Upper Tawang, Tulungla, Bumla, Sela pass areas of West Kameng District, Jidu and adjoining areas of Northern Siang Sikkim: Gnathong, Chhangu, Serrathong, Thangu, Yakthan, ZemaLachen, eegyathathang, Samsinggeling, Cholemu, Lima, Nathula range
2.	Temperate Sub-Alpine Zone (1500–3500 m)	Area: 33564 km ² Rainfall: 2000 mm Temperature: Maximum: 20 ⁰ C Minimum: 11 ⁰ C	Arunachal Pradesh: Tawang, Dirang, Bomdila, Shergaon, areas of West Kameng district, Dibang Valley, Northern part of East Siang, Upper Subansiri district, part of west Siang around Anini and North Eastern part of Lohit district. Meghalaya: Upper Shillong, Mawphlang and Mairang of East Khasi Hills district Manipur: Mao & Maram areas of North district, Ukrul and adjoining areas of East district, Laithang areas of Central district. Sikkim: Karponang, Bordong, Resi, Kangdin, Melli, Param, Lachem, Laichung, Hilley, Yoksum.

			<p>Mizoram: Blue mountain, Halikhan, Tuipang, Nauzuarzo Tiang .</p> <p>Nagaland: Tuensang and Zunhoeboto district, Vangkong area of Wokha district, higher areas of Mokokchung district.</p>
3.	Sub-tropical Hill Zone (1000–1500m)	<p>Area: 29021 km²</p> <p>Rainfall: 2000 mm</p> <p>Temperature:</p> <p>Maximum: 30⁰ C</p> <p>Minimum: 12⁰ C</p>	<p>Arunachal Pradesh: Changyak, Naga and Khonsa area of Tirap district, Basar area of West Siang district.</p> <p>Meghalaya: Jowai sub-division of Jaintia Hills, part of Nongstoin sub-division, Nokrek and Kailash area of West Garo hills and Western part of East Garo Hills.</p> <p>Sikkim: Namchi, Gayzing, Rongli, Rehnok, Mangan, Changthang, Uttre, Gangtok.</p> <p>Mizoram: Whole state except lower valleys of Northern and Western part and area adjoining Cachar district and lower parts of Chhimtuipuii district.</p> <p>Nagaland: Mokokchang district, lower parts of Kohima, Wokha district and Mon district.</p>
4.	Sub-tropical Plain Zone (400-1000 m)	<p>Area: 812 km²</p> <p>Rainfall: 1600 mm</p> <p>Temperature:</p> <p>Maximum: 27⁰ C</p> <p>Minimum: 10⁰ C</p>	<p>Manipur: Imphal Valley</p> <p>Nagaland: Bhaghti & Longnak valley</p> <p>Meghalaya: Umkiang area of Jaintia hills.</p>
5.	Mild Tropical Hill Zone (200-400 m)	<p>Area: 26349 km²</p> <p>Rainfall: 1400mm</p> <p>Temperature:</p> <p>Maximum: 30⁰ C</p> <p>Minimum: 12⁰ C</p>	<p>Arunachal Pradesh: Southern part of lower Subansiri district.</p> <p>Meghalaya: Southern part of Jowai subdivision adjoining Karimganj, Cachar and North Cachar district of Assam, Southern part of Nongpoh sub-division of Ri-Bhoi district, eastern part of east Garo hills and West Khasi Hills.</p> <p>Manipur: Imphal West district, Jiribam area, Churachandpur and Thanlon areas, Moreh area of Tengenoupal district.</p> <p>Sikkim: Rongpoh -East district</p> <p>Mizoram: Lower valley of Northern and Western parts and Chhimtuipuii district.</p> <p>Tripura: Jampui Hills</p> <p>Nagaland: Medziphema area of Dimapur subdivision.</p>

6.	Mild Tropical Plain Zone (0-200 m)	Area: 29333 km ² Rainfall: 2000 mm Temperature: Maximum: 33 ^o C Minimum: 17 ^o C	<p>Arunachal Pradesh: Pasighat area, Singphow area of Tirap district and lower parts of Lohit district.</p> <p>Meghalaya: Lower part of West Garo Hills district</p> <p>Mizoram: Parts of adjoining Cachar district of Assam and North Tripura district</p> <p>Tripura: Major part of Tripura excepting Jampui Hills</p> <p>Nagaland: Southern part of Dimapur subdivision excluding Medziphema area.</p>
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Economic status of Northeast India

The Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) is showing increasing trend in North Eastern region. Assam has the lion share in NE GSDP and it accounts to around 60 per cent followed by Tripura and Meghalaya. The growth of GSDP of NE region showed an increasing trend at the rate of 8.00 per

cent per annum between 2007-08 to 2017-18 period; though in absolute terms, Assam state has the highest GDP among NE states, but the highest growth in GSDP is observed in Mizoram state *i.e.* 12.69 per cent per annum followed by Tripura (9.86 %) and Sikkim (7.20%) and lowest growth rate is recorded in Meghalaya (3.36 %).

In all NE region states, GSDP are showing positive decadal growth. The major contributor to the GSDP of NE region is tertiary sector but agriculture sector is also significantly contributing to GSDP of NE India.

Gross Domestic Product of North Eastern Region (in '000 crores)

Table: Compound annual growth rates of Gross State Domestic Product (2011 to 2017)

Arunachal Pradesh	Assam	Manipur	Meghalaya	Mizoram	Nagaland	Tripura	Sikkim	NEH States
6.28*	8.64*	5.96*	3.36*	12.69*	5.17*	9.86*	7.20*	8.01*

Note: * indicates significant at 1% level of significance, NEH- North Eat Hilly Region

Source: Deka et al. (2020)

Growth in agriculture and allied sectors in Northeast India

The area, production and productivity of major crops and other food items in Northeast India are presented in Table 2. The area under cereal crops is 3.80 million hectares with the total production of 7.82 million tones having the average productivity of 2058 Kg/ha during 2017-18. Cereals occupied the major share in total cropped area followed by vegetables (with area 0.56 million hectares and production 6.05 million tons), oilseeds (area 0.49 million hectares and production 0.38 million tons) and fruits (with area 0.46 million hectares and production 4.51 million tons). The region has produced 0.24 million tons of pulses from 0.27 million hectare area with an average productivity of 828 Kg/ ha during 2017-18. The NE region produced fish to the tune of 446.88 million tons during 2017-18.

Table: Production and productivity of different food items in Northeast India (2017-18)

Particulars	Area (million ha)	Production (million tons)	Productivity (Kg/ha)
Cereal	3.80	7.82	2058
Pulses	0.27	0.24	889
Oilseeds	0.49	0.38	776
Fruits	0.46	4.51	9804
Vegetables	0.56	6.05	10804
Milk	-	1.40	-
Egg (in millions)	-	1065.54	-
Meat	-	0.23	-
Fish	-	4.47	-

Source: Chikkathimme Gowda et al. (2019)

Cropping system of NEH region of India

Cropping system is a broader term comprising the crops and cropping pattern along with their interaction with other agricultural components such as resources, machinery, technologies, environment *etc.* Most of the North Eastern States follow the paddy-paddy, paddy- mustard, paddy-pulses, maize-vegetable, vegetable-vegetable and citrus-ginger.

Cropping diversity of NEH region of India

Temperate zone

Rice, maize, buckwheat, millets, black gram, green gram and arhar Cabbage, cauliflower, knol-khol, broccoli, radish, turnip, beetroot, carrot, garlic, onion, spinach, cucumber, tomato, brinjal, okra, French bean, asparagus, bean, capsicum and peas Apple, pear, peaches, plums, cherries, pistachio, almond, apricot, walnut, chestnut, kiwi fruit and pecan nut.

Subtropical zone

Rice, maize, buckwheat, millets, black gram, green gram, sesame and arhar. Brinjal, tomato, okra, beans (broad, rajma, bush and pole French bean), peas, carrot, radish, turnip, cole crops, leafy vegetables (palak, methi, mustard), onion, garlic, chili and capsicum, potato, sweet potato, colocasia, yams, alocasia and chow chow. Mango, guava, citrus, mandarin orange, litchi, low chilling peaches, pears, plums, almond, aonla. Rose, gladiolus, orchids, carnation, chrysanthemum, marigold, petunia, large number of other ornamental and foliage plants.

Tropical zone

Rice, maize, buckwheat, millets, black gram, green gram and arhar. Brinjal, tomato, okra, beans (broad, bush, climbing), gourds (bottle, ridge, ash, bitter), cowpea, amaranthus, pumpkin, mustard. Cassava, sweet potato, amorphophallus, dioscorea, yams, coleus, colocasia, tree bean. Mango, citrus, Assam lemon, banana, pineapple, papaya, grapes, sapota, passion fruit, water melon, snape melon. Coconut, arecanut, cashew, oil palm, rubber, cocoa, tea, tree tomato, coffee and cinnamom. Turmeric, ginger, large cardamom, pepper. Rose, chrysanthemum, jasmine, marigold, balsum, orchids, tube rose, gerbera, anthurium.

Medicinal plants flora and fauna in NEH region of India

North-eastern India is highly diverse biologically within Indian Sub-continent and have supported around 300 species of mammals, 977 species of birds, 176 species of reptiles, 110 species of Amphibians, 422 species of fishes, above 11,586 species of Invertebrates, 10,000 species of flowering plants (above 50% of Indian flora), 850 species of medicinal and aeromatic plants and 825 species of orchids .

High value spices, cereals and fruits in NEH region of India

Among the commercial fruits of the country, maximum diversity in citrus, banana and jack fruit are found in Northeast India. A large number of diversity in other tropical and subtropical fruits belonging to the genera *Garcinia*, *Artocarpus*, *Phyllanthus*, *Annona*, *Averrhoa*, *Persia*, *Aegle*, *Passiflora* and *Tamarindus* etc. are reported from the region. Northeast India is also rich in different genotypes of cucurbits, solanaceous vegetables, ginger, turmeric, bamboo, leafy vegetables etc. Northeast India is the citrus depository of our country where many citrus species are originated. Khasi mandarin (*Citrus reticulata*) is widely cultivated in Northeast India and Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) is also commercially grown in some of the places in the region. Apart from the most commonly cultivated species *Citrus indica* Tanaka (Indian wild orange), *C. latipes* (Swingle), *C. ichangensis* Swingle (Ichang Papeda), *C. medica*, *Citrus assamensis*, *Citrus macroptera* and *C. hystrix* were reported to occur in the subtropical forests of North-East India and the foot hills of the East Himalayas.

Diversity of microbes in NEH region of India

North east India, a biodiversity hotspot, is known for its rich faunal diversity that includes hornbills, elephants and the one-horned rhinoceros. However, the region's vibrant microbial diversity has remained largely obscure. A team of researchers from the North-Eastern Hill University in Shillong, Meghalaya have now developed a web-based microbe database that details information about soil microbes in north east India. The database, called the North East India Microbial Database (NEMiD), currently has information on 229 bacteria and fungi isolated from Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Tripura, Sikkim and parts of North Bengal.

Irrigation system in NEH region of India

NER is endowed with 33% of the country's water resources. It receives annual rainfall ranging from 2,480 mm to 6,350 mm. The annual water availability of 16,500 cubic meters per capita and 44,180 cubic meters per hectare is the highest in the country. Due to high rainfall, NER has an inherent advantage to exploit rain-water harvesting. However, the rate of harnessing and utilizing irrigation potential has been low since only 11% of net cultivable land is irrigated. Accelerated

Irrigation Benefit Program (AIBP) emphasizes exploiting surface irrigation through Minor Irrigation (MI) schemes in NER. Under MI schemes, an irrigation potential of 46,500 hectares has been created of which 34,300 hectares (73.76%) are being utilized. Besides, irrigation potential of 2,93,110 hectares under Bharat Nirman is targeted comprising 1,09,140 hectares under major and medium irrigation and 1,83,970 hectares under MI schemes. North Eastern Council (NEC) cautions against intensive exploitation of underground water as hazardous elements have been found at several locations.

Food grains production vis-a-vis requirement in NE region

By and large the North Eastern region of India is deficit in food grains production and this is the cause of concern of all policy makers and technologists. The rough estimates prepared as per ICMR recommendation clearly indicates that the region would require an approximately 80.78 lakh tons of cereals, 4.43 lakh tons of pulses, 6.06 lakh tons of oilseeds, 6.05 lakh tons of fruits and

20.20 lakh tons of vegetables for its projected population of 55.33 million in 2030 (Population Projections of India and States 2011-2036). Over the years the demand for food grains has shown increasing trend with the increasing population. Assam state has the largest population in NE region and requires around 69 per cent of total cereals demand followed by Tripura, Meghalaya, Manipur, Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh and Sikkim during 2030. Similar trend is observed for all the field crops including horticultural crops, fishery, livestock and poultry sector. The supply projection of field crops, horticulture, livestock, poultry and fishery sector for the period 2030 is presented in Table 9. As per the projections, cereals produced during 2030 in NE region would be around 95.58 lakh ton which is 15.48 percent more than the requirement. Oilseeds, pulses and vegetables have however showed substantial deficit in their production in contrast to fruits production, which has shown strong growth in the next decade. Livestock products such as milk, meat and eggs may become deficit as per the ICMR recommendation for the anticipated population as per the present trend of the growth. Only fish production is expected to meet its requirement in coming decade. The deficit in pulse production in NE region of India is around 82 per cent against its requirements as per ICMR recommendation.

Table: Production and requirement of food grains in Northeast India for 2030

North East Hill region	Demand (lakh tons)	Supply (lakh tons)	Deficit/Surplus (lakh tons)	Share of deficit/surplus in projected supply (%)
Cereals	80.78	95.58	14.79	15.48
Pulses	4.43	3.12	-1.31	-42.05
Oilseeds	6.06	4.55	-1.51	-33.06
Fruits	25.14	52.86	+27.72	52.44
Vegetables	62.53	73.90	+11.37	15.39
Milk	27.67	16.89	-10.78	-63.82
Fish	2.88	6.84	3.96	57.92
Meat	6.06	3.26	-2.80	-85.87
Egg (lakh No.)	99594	13547	-86047	-635.17

Source: ICMR RDA 2010: Per capita consumption: Milk-50kg/yr ; meat:10.95kg/yr; egg:180 nos/yr; pulses:8kg/yr; vegetables:300g/day; oils:30g; fruits:120g; cereals: 400g/day; Fish:100g/week.

Status of CAU, Imphal in NEH region of India

The Central Agricultural University was established by an act of Parliament, the Central Agricultural University Act 1992 (No.40 of 1992). The Act came into effect on 26 January 1993 with the issue of necessary notification by the Department of Agricultural Research and Education (DARE), Government of India. The university became functional with the joining of the first vice-chancellor on 13 September 1993. The jurisdiction of the university extends to seven NEH states: Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Sikkim, Nagaland and Tripura.

The University at present has 13 colleges as well as 6 (six) KVKs to help and address the problems that farmers face in different aspects of agriculture. Also, these centers are expected to be a link between agricultural scientists located in colleges and farmers to disseminate the agricultural know-how and also get feedback to find solutions to new problems or fine-tune an existing solution for a given problem. Recently the University also established six (6) technology verification centers known as Multi-Technology Testing Centre (MTTC) and 6 Vocational Training Centers (VTC) in different states viz., Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Sikkim, and Tripura. It is expected that these centers will verify the new technologies developed by scientists at different locations for their adaptability so that technology is presented to the end user the farmer in the finest form for quick adoption thereby helping a farmer achieve more on his investment and thereby helping the country in furthering the sustainable development goals in agriculture and allied sciences. The University offers 9 Undergraduate, 45 Masters and 25 Ph. D. Degree Programmes in different subjects/disciplines of Agriculture & Allied Sciences through its 13 constituent colleges located in seven states of the NE Region of India. Since inception till 2021, 5255 students have passed out from the University (3836 graduates, 1344 post-graduates & 75 Ph. Ds). 125 ex-students are working as ARS Scientists, 120 as University/College faculty, 60 as SMS in KVKs, 453 are employed in Central/ State Govt. Dept, 129 in private firms, 55 in Banking sector and 12 in civil services conducted by UPSC & state civil services.

CONCLUSION

North Eastern region of India is known for its diversified cultural heritage and biodiversity. NE region is predominantly agrarian and practice subsistence agriculture. Majority of the workforce are engaged in agriculture and allied sector for livelihood. In recent years, due to appropriate policy initiatives by the government, the progress in Agriculture in the region is visible and few states like Assam, Manipur, Nagaland and Tripura are now self sufficient in rice production. Likewise, the annual growth in Fishery sector in the region in terms of production is more than 5 % during 2008-18. Moreover, by 2030, the region would have surplus production in cereals, fruits and fish even though it would be deficient in production of pulses, oilseeds, milk, meet and egg etc. The potentiality of agriculture in the region is very vast and with appropriate market let production system planning coupled with technology injection and participation of young educated people, the agriculture in the region would grow substantially to bridge the gap between production and demand in next few years. It is expected that in this fiscal, the share of agriculture in state GDP in the region would increase due to the favorable rainfall pattern as indicted by IMD coupled with the much needed measures announced by Govt. of India through its Aatmanirbhar Bharat initiative.

References

- Deka BC, Singha AK, Parisa D and Amrutha P. (2020). Prospects of Northeast Agriculture in post COVID 19 scenario. Pub: ICAR- ATARI, Umiam, Meghalaya, pp-1-221.
- Chikkathimme Gowda HR, Amrutha T, Ragavendra KJ and Shivkumar. (2019). Millets Production and Prospects in India: An Economic Overview, Green Farming, 10(3), pp: 35-39.
- Bhatt BP, Jat ML, Arunachalam A, Pattanayak A and Prakash N. (2019). Roadmap for Agricultural Development in North-Eastern Hill (NEH) Region, India. Policy Brief, p. 8. Published by Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi.

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